

Event metadata

Event title	Deciphering AI for the Life Sciences
Event type	Webinar
Date of event	18/03/2025
Time of event	12pm AEDT
Topic description	<p>Curious about how Artificial Intelligence (AI) is transforming life sciences?</p> <p>AI is reshaping life sciences by enabling researchers to analyze complex datasets, automate workflows, and gain deeper insights into biological processes. This introductory webinar will break down AI concepts, clarify key terminology, and showcase real-world examples of AI applications in the life sciences.</p>
Format description	Webinar presentation followed by a brief question and answer session
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/ailifesciences-2025
Licence	Materials are shared under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International agreement unless otherwise stated on the materials
Keywords	Machine Learning http://edamontology.org/topic_3474 Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091
Contact	training@biocommons.org.au
Audience	<p>Who the webinar is for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wet lab scientists with minimal computational background and eager to apply AI to their experimental workflows • Bioinformaticians/computational scientists with some programming experience but new to AI, interested in integrating AI in their pipelines • Research leads and decision-makers interested in the strategic impact of AI
Prerequisites	None

Technical requirements	None
Learning outcomes	<p>By the end of this webinar you should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define key AI-related terms • Understand the historical progression of AI and how it has evolved to impact life sciences • Recognise key AI applications in specific life science domains • Understand the benefits and limitations of AI • Navigate available learning resources to explore AI further
Speakers	Dr Benjamin Goudey, AI Technical Lead, Australian BioCommons
Training materials	<p>Files and materials included in this record:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Event metadata (PDF): Information about the event including, description, event URL, learning objectives, prerequisites, technical requirements etc. • Deciphering AI for the Life Sciences (PDF): A PDF copy of the slides presented during the webinar. <p>Materials shared elsewhere:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A recording of this webinar is available on the Australian BioCommons YouTube Channel: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sbVzcrD-wkQ
Related material	None